

1 **Understanding climate's influence on the extinction of *Oreopithecus* (late Miocene, Tusco-**
2 **Sardinian palaeobioprovince, Italy)**

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10

11 **Abstract**

12 Despite its long history of scientific study, the causes underlying the extinction of the insular
13 hominoid *Oreopithecus bambolii* are still a matter of ongoing debate. While some authors
14 consider intense tectonism and invading species the cause of its extinction ca. 6.7 Ma, others
15 propose climatic change as the main contributing factor. We rely on long-term patterns of tooth
16 wear and hypsodonty of the Baccinello and Fiume Santo herbivore-faunas to reconstruct
17 changes in habitat prior to, during and after the extinction. While a mosaic of habitats was
18 represented in Baccinello V1 (as shown by a record of browsers, mixed feeders and species
19 engaged in grazing), more closed forests (higher proportion of browsers, shortage of mixed
20 feeders and lack of grazers) characterised Baccinello V2. Finally, there was a partial loss of
21 canopy cover and development of open-patches and low-abrasive grasses in Baccinello V3 (as
22 denoted by new records of taxa involved in grazing)—although still dominated by a forested
23 habitat (since browse was a component in all diets). Our results provide evidence for two
24 perceptible shifts in climate, one between 8.1-7.1 Ma and other ca. 6.7 Ma, though this latter
25 was not drastic enough to lead to intensive forest loss, substantially alter the local vegetation or
26 affect *Oreopithecus* lifestyle—especially if considering the growing evidence of its versatile

27 diet. Although the disappearance of *Oreopithecus* is complex, our data reject the hypothesis of
28 environmental change as the main factor in the extinction of *Oreopithecus* and Maremma fauna.
29 When our results are analyzed together with other evidence, faunal interaction and predation by
30 invading species from mainland Europe seems to be the most parsimonious explanation for this
31 extinction event. This contrasts with European hominoid extinctions that were associated with
32 major climatic shifts that led to environmental uniformity and restriction of the preferred
33 habitats of Miocene apes.

34 **Key words:** Neogene, Europe, ungulates, hominoids, paleoecology, tooth wear

35

36 **1. Introduction**

37

38 The late middle and late Miocene is an important time period for understanding the radiation
39 of hominoids in Eurasia. Although much recent progress has been made in examining their
40 dispersal from Africa into Eurasia during the middle Miocene (Andrews and Kelley, 2007),
41 their subsequent radiation (see Alba, 2012 and references therein) and the drivers of their
42 gradual extinction in the late Miocene (Merceron et al., 2010; Casanovas-Vilar et al., 2011;
43 DeMiguel et al., 2014), the causes that underlie the disappearance of *Oreopithecus bambolii*—
44 the latest surviving Western Eurasian ape—still remain open to debate.

45 *Oreopithecus* was a large-bodied hominoid from the late Miocene of the Tusco-Sardinian
46 paleobioprovince (Italy) that lived in conditions of insularity (Bernor et al., 2001; Rook et al.,
47 2006) between ca. 8.1 Ma and 6.7 Ma (Rook, 2016) and evolved a unique mixture of primitive
48 and derived anatomical features which precludes interpretations of its phylogeny, history and
49 paleobiology. Despite this apparent lack of connection with most other European hominoids,
50 *Oreopithecus* has a crucial role for understanding stem hominoid evolution and, particularly, the
51 mechanism driving the extinction of late Miocene apes (DeMiguel et al., 2014).

52 *Oreopithecus* went extinct at ca. 6.7 Ma (Rook, 2009; Rook et al., 2011), which contrasts
53 strongly with most other ape extinctions in Eurasia, ultimately related to an increase in

54 environmental uniformity and the resulting loss of habitat suitability (Merceron et al., 2010;
55 DeMiguel et al., 2014). In Western and Central Europe, this sharp decline has been related to
56 changes toward increased seasonality and lower temperatures, with the substitution of fruit-rich
57 evergreen (sub)tropical forests by more deciduous trees (Alba, 2012; DeMiguel et al., 2014). At
58 least in the Catalan coastal basins (with a large and outstanding record of Miocene primates,
59 including among others *Pierolapithecus*, *Anoiapithecus*, *Dryopithecus* and *Hispanopithecus*)
60 this process was gradual, implying the fragmentation of habitats in which (sub)tropical elements
61 became progressively restricted to lowland humid areas (see DeMiguel et al., 2014 and
62 references therein). The last occurrence (ca. 10 Ma) of *Hispanopithecus* (*Rudapithecus*)
63 *hungaricus* at Rudabanya (Hungary) was also related to climate change and final regression of
64 Lake Pannon (Bernor et al., 2004; Armour-Chelu et al., 2005 and relevant references therein). In
65 Eastern Europe, *Ouranopithecus* survived longer than these other Western and Central
66 European counterparts (ca. 8.0-7.5 vs. 9.5 Ma), probably due to specialized dietary and
67 anatomical adaptations to more open and arid habitats (Merceron et al., 2010). Although its
68 extinction did not coincide with any major climatic shift, it might be similarly related to strong
69 seasonal fluctuation (Merceron et al., 2013).

70 *Oreopithecus* survived this major (Vallesian-Turolian) extinction event in the latest Miocene
71 Tusco-Sardinian paleobioprovince, but its extinction does not offer much insight with regard to
72 that of these other hominoids from mainland Europe. Research findings, indeed, have yielded
73 conflicting results regarding its disappearance. While some works attribute its extinction and the
74 replacement of its endemic associated fauna to a marked shift from warm and humid conditions
75 to an inconsistent climate regime (Benvenuti et al., 1994; Bernor et al., 2001; Ligios et al.,
76 2008), others show no relation to any significant change in climate or habitat, but rather to the
77 connection of its insular ecosystem to the mainland ca. 6.7 Ma (Rook et al., 2011; Matson et al.,
78 2012; Nelson and Rook, 2016) and intensive interaction with invading non-endemic fauna like
79 *Hippotherium*, *Dicerorhinus*, *Propotamochoerus*, *Machairodus*, etc (Bernor et al., 2001; Rook et
80 al., 2011).

81 Together with this controversial hominoid, there is a substantial record of fossil herbivorous
82 mammals and a preponderance of ruminants, which are particularly suitable for the
83 reconstructions of terrestrial environments and habitat, and the evolution of climate (DeMiguel
84 et al., 2010, 2011). Given such unusual abundance of late Miocene plant-eating taxa (mostly
85 bovids belonging to the genus *Maremmia* and to Antilopini species—such as *Tyrrhenotragus*—,
86 but also other ruminants and equids) during the Baccinello-Cinigiano sequence, this
87 investigation relies on evidence of their diets (through quantitative analyses of tooth wear) and
88 ecologically-dependent traits to search for signs of the existence of changes in climate during
89 the whole sequence and reconstruct *Oreopithecus*' habitat and changes in habitat that may have
90 ultimately led to its extinction (our working hypothesis here). Our investigation thus yields
91 direct data on the feeding behavior and dietary guilds of the herbivorous faunas, thereby
92 providing evidence of the vegetation composition and habitat structure of the local ecosystems.
93 To do so, dental wear and hypsodonty are first examined for the interval belonging to V1, V2
94 and Fiume Santo to provide a reconstruction of the vegetation mosaic and environments at a
95 time when *Oreopithecus* was present. Then, results are reported for V3 biozone to reconstruct
96 the habitat just after *Oreopithecus* went extinct. Finally, we analyse our data together with
97 previous results from other works for this late Miocene taxon to re-evaluate and further refine
98 the most likely mechanisms driving the eventual extinction of the last European hominoid.
99

100 **2. Materials and methods**

101

102 *2.1. Sample*

103 We sampled for analysis a total of 183 individuals from 12 fossil ungulate taxa (artiodactyls and
104 perissodactyls) (see Table 1) from the Baccinello-Cinigiano sequence (Tuscany, Central Italy),
105 which comprises three local vertebrate biozones (from oldest to youngest: V1, V2 and V3)
106 (Lorenz, 1968; Engesser, 1989; Rook, 2016), and other localities of the so-called Tusco
107 Sardinian paleobioprovince (Fig. 1). *O. bambolii* is reported in zones V1 and V2, which include
108 a very peculiar and highly endemic faunal complex as well—referred to as the “Maremma

109 fauna” or “*Oreopithecus* Zone Faunas”—, very different from coeval faunas either from
110 European or African continental realms (Benvenuti et al., 1994; Bernor et al., 2001). The
111 material considered for study belongs to different localities and reflects differences in faunal
112 composition (Table 1). i) Fauna (*Maremmia haupti*, *Turritragus casteanensis* and
113 *Umbrotherium azzarolii*) from V1 level including Ribolla, Casteani and Serrazzano (ca. 8.3–8.1
114 Ma, upper part of chron C4r). ii) V2 fauna (such as *Maremmia lorenzi*, *Maremmia cf. lorenzi*,
115 *Tyrrhenotragus gracillimus*, *Turritragus casteanensis*, ?Antilopini gen. and sp. indet., *Etruria*
116 *viallii* and *Umbrotherium azzarolii*) that account for the last representatives (that is, the pre-
117 extinction interval) of the Maremma assemblage and *Oreopithecus*, represented by Podere la
118 Crocina and Montebamboli, and the comparable in age Fiume Santo assemblage (ca. 7.1–6.7,
119 chron C3Ar) (Abbazzi et al., 2008). iii) V3 assemblage (*Hippotherium malpassii*, *Paracervulus*
120 *cf. australis*, *Procacpreolus cf. loczyi* and *Tuscomeryx huerzeleri*) records a great faunal renewal
121 of mainland origin, including the post-extinction interval localities of Ribaldella, Podere
122 Firenze, Podere La Locca, Podere Le Pigne, Cinigiano, Fosso del Pian Calcinaio and Galassi
123 (ca. 6.7–6.4 Ma, chron C3An.2n) (Rook et al., 1999a; Bernor et al., 2001, 2011). The last
124 updated chronology of the Baccinello Basin sediments is used following magnetostratigraphic
125 data (Rook et al., 2011) based on the geopolarity timescale GPTS 2004 (Lourens et al., 2004).
126 Note that small bovids previously considered as belonging to Neotragini by Abazzi et al. (2008)
127 are here considered Antilopini according to the updated revision of the group by Bärmann et al.
128 (2013) and Bärmann and Schikora (2014). All studied specimens from the Baccinello-Cinigiano
129 Basin are housed at the Museo di Storia Naturale (Sezione Geologia e Paleontologia) of the
130 University of Florence (Italy), while the specimens from Fiume Santo belong to the
131 Soprintendenza per i Beni Archeologici per le Province di Sassari e Nuoro (sample studied
132 while on loan to the Vertebrate Paleontology Laboratory of the Earth Sciences Department,
133 University of Florence).

134

135 *2.2. Long-term patterns of tooth wear*

136 The study of diets has received increasing attention in paleontological research over the past
137 several decades. Among the various methods of paleoenvironmental and paleoecological
138 reconstruction, analyses based on either stable isotope geochemistry or dental wear are the most
139 widely used as they provide direct information on the properties of the foods consumed and are
140 independent from adaptation. Geochemical methods, such as carbon isotopic ratios derived from
141 fossil tooth enamel are based on the carbon isotopic distinction between C₃ and C₄
142 photosynthetic pathways. Carbon and oxygen stable isotope analyses from matter and
143 pedogenic carbonate in paleosols from the Baccinello Basin (Matson et al., 2012) and inorganic
144 carbonate in tooth enamel (Nelson and Rook, 2016) have been recently published for
145 *Oreopithecus* and its associated faunas. The direct inspection of tooth wear patterns in plant-
146 eating mammals allows a non-destructive examination of the data sets. As a result, one of the
147 most powerful methods for inferring dietary behavior in extinct taxa and reconstructing past
148 climates and paleoecology, based on the strong and consistent association between macroscopic
149 tooth wear and the physical properties of the chewed foods, is used in this work.

150 Dental mesowear measures the relative amounts of attritional and abrasive wear that food
151 items exert on the occlusal enamel of ungulate teeth (Fortelius and Solounias, 2000), thus
152 reflecting the prolonged effect (months, years) of tooth wear throughout an animal's lifespan.
153 Originally proposed for the second upper molars, this method has been subsequently extended
154 to all the cheek teeth (DeMiguel et al., 2010, 2011). Occlusal relief (OR; high or low, the
155 relative difference in height between the tip of the cusps and the intercusp valley) and molar
156 cusp shape (MCS; sharp, rounded or blunt) were examined and qualitatively scored, and
157 individual MCS and OR scores were converted into a single mesowear score (MS) for each
158 fossil species following Rivals et al. (2009). A score of 0 is given to teeth with a combination
159 of high relief and sharp cusps; 1 to teeth with high relief and rounded cusps; 2 to teeth with low
160 relief and rounded cusps; 2.5 to teeth with low relief and sharp cusps; and 3 to teeth with low
161 relief and blunt cusps. As a baseline sample, a set of 45 extant ungulate (artiodactyl and
162 perissodactyl) species (1764 specimens) with well-known diets (Fortelius and Solounias, 2000)

163 was used for comparative purpose. The dataset was partitioned into browsing ($n=9$), mixed
164 feeding ($n=25$) and grazing ($n=11$) feeding categories.

165

166 *2.3. Molar crown height*

167 Because hypsodonty is fundamentally an adaptive response to increasing demands for wear
168 tolerance and functional durability as a consequence of the development of more abrasives in a
169 progressively more open and dry-adapted vegetation (Fortelius et al., 2002), it yields
170 information about habitat structure (especially aridity degree) and ecology (Janis, 1988). The
171 mean hypsodonty value was calculated for each ungulate species by averaging ordinate scores.
172 Measurements were taken on unworn molars or those least affected by wear. The values of the
173 height to length ratio of the upper (second, if available) molars were determined, and teeth
174 classified as brachydont (with a Hypsodonty Index (HI) of less than 1.5), mesodont (HI of 1.5-
175 3) and hypsodont ($HI > 3$) (Janis, 1988).

176

177 *2.4. Statistical tests*

178 Hierarchical, complete-linkage (Ward's method) cluster analyses based on Euclidean
179 distances, and discriminant Canonical Variate Analyses (CVA) were performed to characterize
180 dietary traits of species following DeMiguel (2016), which provides a more detailed
181 explanation. The tests were developed using the combination of rounded and blunt cusps, and
182 high relief as criterion variables. Cluster analysis was intended to explore the similarities in
183 mesowear patterns between extant ungulates and fossil species. CVA, in turn, was intended to
184 evaluate the reliability of these mesowear variables for distinguishing between the various
185 dietary categories defined for extant taxa, as well as to classify fossils to these categories. Extant
186 ungulate species were thus included a priori in one of the three dietary categories described
187 above, whereas the extinct taxa were left unclassified and classified a posteriori on the basis of
188 the classification probabilities derived by the analysis from Mahalanobis squared distances to
189 extant group centroids.

190

191 3. Results

192

193 3.1. Baccinello V1 assemblage (8.3–8.1 Ma)

194 In Baccinello V1, *U. azzarolii* shows occlusal enamel surfaces with a predominance of sharp
195 cusps and high relief, while *M. haupti* and *T. casteanensis* consist of nearly 50% pS-pR
196 (percentage of specimens with sharp and rounded cusps, respectively) and 50% pH-pL
197 (percentage of specimens with high and low relief, respectively) (see Table 1 for specific
198 values). Fossil taxa do not show any incidence of blunt cusps. The scores (mesowear score; MS)
199 recorded cover a wide range of levels in food abrasiveness, from 0 in *U. azzarolii* (as in the
200 extant *Alces alces* and *Rhinoceros sondaicus*), 1.3 in *T. casteanensis* (similar to *Hippotragus*
201 *niger*), to 1.7 in *M. haupti* (comparable to the grazer *Alcelaphus buselaphus*). All these facts
202 presumably exclude the intake of abrasives, such as phytolith-rich grasses and exogenous dust
203 and grit (DeMiguel, 2016), in the diet of *U. azzarolii* (although only one suitable specimen, the
204 type maxillary bone from Casteani, is available for study—, while point to considerable larger
205 amounts of abrasive material in the diet of the fossil bovids and abrasion-dominated wear
206 surfaces for these taxa.

207

208 3.2. Baccinello V2 assemblage (7.1–6.7 Ma)

209 Fossil specimens of *T. gracillimus* have mesowear patterns characterised by a predominance
210 of sharp cusps (pS=70%) and high relief (pH nearly 91%), and the species has an average MS of
211 0.4 (similar to that of the extant browser *Antilocapra americana* MS=0.37 and the browse-
212 dominated mixed feeder *Tragelaphus imberbis* MS=0.42). The specimens of *M. haupti* also
213 display a predominance of sharp cusps (pS=100%) but account for higher percentages of low
214 relief (pL=50%) and and higher MS (MS=1.25 similar to that of the mixed feeder *Boselaphus*
215 *tragocamelus* MS=1.13). This points to somewhat larger amounts of abrasive material in the
216 diet of *M. haupti* than in *T. gracillimus*. Despite this, mesowear signals reveal attrition-

217 dominated signals and low levels of dietary abrasion for the bovids of the V2 zone (Table 1),
218 mostly comparable with the pattern of modern bovids committed to browsing.

219

220 3.3. Fiume Santo assemblage (7.1–6.7 Ma)

221 Despite the extraordinary taxonomic diversity of the Fiume Santo community (Abbazzi et
222 al., 2008), with seven artiodactyl species being recorded, the dental wear pattern is relatively
223 homogeneous. Most of the fossil species display mesowear comprised of sharp cusps and high
224 relief (pS and pH around 100%; Table 1), and MS that cover a narrow range of (low) levels in
225 food abrasives (from 0 to 0.23), as found in extant leaf browsers (such as *A. alces* or *Okapia*
226 *johnstoni*). This pattern is observed for *U. azzarolii*, *T. gracillimus*, *E. viallii*, *T. casteanensis*
227 and the ?Antilopini gen. and sp. indet. In contrast, *Maremmia* cf. *lorenzi* shows both stronger
228 rounding (pR=50%) and much lower relief (pL=37.1%), though it also displays significant
229 incidence of sharp (pS=46.8%) and some blunt (percentage of specimens with blunt cusps;
230 pB=3.2%) apices, and an overall MS of 1.18. Although only two fossil specimens are available,
231 *M. lorenzi* also has more rounded apices (pR=100%) and high relief (pH=100%), and records a
232 score of 1. This points to higher levels of abrasion in the diets of the *Maremmia* species than the
233 remaining taxa, as typical of some modern mixed feeders (e.g., *B. tragocamelus* and *Syncerus*
234 *caffer* MS~1).

235

236 3.4. Oreopithecus post-extinction assemblage (ca. 6.7–6.4 Ma)

237 Faunas following the extinction of *Oreopithecus* show occlusal enamel surfaces with a
238 predominance of high occlusal relief (pH=100%), with the exception of the equid
239 *Hippotherium malpassii* which shows an important incidence of low relief (pL=76.5%), and
240 variation in the proportion of rounded cusps depending on the species. *H. malpassii* and the
241 cervid *Paracervulus* cf. *australis* have around 50% sharp and 50% rounded cusps (Table 1),
242 whereas the moschid *Tuscomeryx huerzeleri* and the cervid *Procapreolus* cf. *loczyi* have more
243 rounded apices (pR=75% and 71.4%, respectively). It is worth noting that species do not show
244 any incidence of blunt cusps. Fossil taxa cover a wide range of MS, ranging from low (0.42 in

245 *P. cf. australis*—similar to the browser *A. americana*) to intermediate (0.71 and 0.75 in *P. cf.*
246 *loczyi* and *T. huerzeleri*, respectively—comparable to the mixed feeders *. Capricornis*
247 *sumatraensis* and *Ovibos moschatus*) and high (1.76 in *H. malpassii*—similar to the grazer *A.*
248 *buselaphus*).

249

250 3.5. Hypsodonty analysis

251 It is apparent that the fossil fauna represents a certain variability in molar crown height, with
252 most of the ruminants (*P. cf. australis*, *T. huerzeleri* and *P. cf. loczyi*) from the V3 post-
253 extinction assemblage (with the exception of *H. malpassii*) being brachydont species (HI
254 ranging from 0.5 to 1.4; see Table 1), *U. azzarolii* having a mesodont dentition (HI=1.72),
255 although being near the brachydont condition, and the remaining fossils displaying a
256 considerable hypsodonty (HI 3.3 to 5.1). These latter also include *H. malpassii* (as expected for
257 an equid), for which mean hypsodonty (HI=2.9) is near the lower threshold of this
258 morphological condition despite the value being calculated from (the only available) teeth
259 showing some significant wear.

260 The bivariate plot of hypsodonty index vs. the mesowear score of extant and fossil ungulates
261 (Fig. 2) supports our interpretations. Apart from the fact that brachydont species are only
262 recorded in the association of Baccinello V3, we do not see any other remarkable pattern
263 through time in hypsodonty. The species from Baccinello V1 fall into the browser, mixed feeder
264 and grazer dietary domains with mesodont and hypsodont dentitions, whereas species from
265 Baccinello V2 and Fiume Santo occur in the browser and mixed feeder group with a
266 combination of mesodont and hypsodont tooth crowns. Finally, the ungulates from Baccinello
267 V3 overlap mostly between the browser and mixed feeder domains having brachydont teeth,
268 while *H. malpassii* is the only species plotted among the modern grazers and showing a higher
269 degree of hypsodonty.

270

271 3.6. Multivariate statistics

272 A first cluster analysis based on mesowear attributes (rounded and blunt cusp shape and high
273 relief) (Fig. 3) yields two main groups, and separates extant browsers and some mixed feeders
274 (cluster A) from the remaining mixed feeders and grazers/grass-dominated mixed feeders
275 (cluster B). Most of the species from Fiume Santo (with the exception of specimens of
276 *Maremmia*) are grouped with extant leaf browsers (*A. alces*, *O. virginianus*, etc) in subcluster
277 A1, as well as *U. azzarolii* from Baccinello V1. *T. gracillimus* from Baccinello V2 and
278 *Paracervulus cf. australis* from the V3 fauna interval cluster in turn in A2, together with the
279 remaining extant browsers and several mixed feeders (*Antidorcas marsupialis*, *T. imberbis* and
280 *Capra ibex*) which are characterized by higher incidences of rounded apices. In contrast,
281 *Procapreolus cf. loczyi* and *T. huerzeleri* from the V3 post-extinction assemblage and *M.*
282 *lorenzi* from Fiume Santo are grouped in B1; with the two former being close to extant mixed
283 feeders and the latter clustering with extant grazers (*Kobus ellipsiprymnus* and *Redunca*
284 *redunca*) and grass-dominated mixed feeders (*S. caffer*). Finally, the remaining species (*M.*
285 *haupti* and *T. casteanensis* from Baccinello V1, *M. haupti* from Baccinello V2, *Maremmia cf.*
286 *lorenzi* from Fiume Santo, and *H. malpassii* from the post-extinction assemblage) are grouped
287 in B2, mostly with grazer species such as *A. buselaphus*, *Connochaetus taurinus*, etc. (thereby
288 suggesting tendencies towards mixed feeding and grazing habits). Particular attention is given to
289 the emplacement in the dendrogram of all these species, as they are in a set that contains only
290 fossil taxa. This fact could indicate that grasses and other abrasives were present (to a greater or
291 lesser degree) in all the assemblages.

292 The CVA (Fig. 4, Table 2 and 3) provides a satisfactory dietary discrimination, with 77.8%
293 of extant taxa (and 68.9% in cross-validation) correctly classified according to a conservative
294 dietary classification of the species. CV1 separates grazers and grass-dominated mixed feeders
295 (positive values in the plot) from browsers and browse-dominated mixed feeders (negative
296 values) mostly on the basis of cusp shape, whereas CV2 is more influenced by occlusal relief
297 and does not allow as clear a distinction among dietary types as CV1 (Fig. 4A). Overall, the
298 analysis (Table 3, Fig. 4A) indicates that the assemblage of Baccinello V1 supported browser
299 (*U. azzarolii*), mixed feeder (*T. casteanensis*) and grazer (*M. haupti*) species; the artiodactyls

300 from the Baccinello V2 and Fiume Santo assemblages are considered to be mixed feeders (*M.*
301 *lorenzi* and *M. cf. lorenzi*) and browsers (all the remaining); and the faunas following the
302 extinction of *Oreopithecus* are considered to be browsers (*P. cf. australis*), mixed feeders (*T.*
303 *huerzeleri* and *P. cf. loczyi*) and grazers (*H. malpassii*), although only the sample of the equid is
304 large enough to provide consistent results. Particular attention is given to the bovid *M. haupti*,
305 as it occurred in both V1 and V2 biozones. Its wear signature in the former assemblage is
306 closest to the grazing end of the dietary continuum, whereas the population from the assemblage
307 V2 is closer to the browsing one. On the other hand, CVA results based on a more radical
308 dietary classification of the species (with 75.6% of extant taxa correctly classified, and 73.3% in
309 cross-validation) (Fig. 4B) differ from those of the conservative classification for only three
310 fossil taxa: *M. haupti* (Baccinello V1 assemblage) and *H. malpassii* (post-extinction
311 assemblage) moved from the grazer class towards the mixed feeder, whereas *M. lorenzi* (Fiume
312 Santo assemblage) moved from the mixed feeder towards the grazing diet (Table 3, Fig. 4B).
313 This would imply that the last showed a certain tendency towards grazing despite being a mixed
314 feeder (i.e., grass-dominated mixed feeder), and that the other two are next to grazers in
315 mesowear evaluation, though they cannot be considered as strict (or purely) grazers.
316 Accordingly, they are best considered as species strongly engaged in grazing.

317

318 **4. Discussion**

319

320 *4.1. Dietary traits and ecology of fossil herbivore communities*

321 Large mammalian herbivore communities of *Oreopithecus* and post-*Oreopithecus* faunas are
322 quite similar (although some differences can be observed) in the composition of the dietary
323 regimes of their members, but they clearly differ in the proportion of dietary traits represented.

324 Dental wear signatures reflect the existence of a variable level of abrasion and diversity of
325 feeding adaptations in the Baccinello V1 assemblage, as denoted by the presence of a strict
326 browser (*U. azzarolii*), a mixed feeder (*T. casteanensis*) and a species (*M. haupti*) engaged in
327 grazing, probably as a grass-dominated mixed feeder. In contrast, Fiume Santo and V2 faunas

328 consistently yield a range of wear that is quite narrow in the sense that it represents low abrasion
329 overall for most of the species. There is a higher presence of browsing signatures in this interval
330 (*M. haupti*, *T. gracillimus*, *U. azzarolii*, *E. viallii*, *T. casteanensis* and the ?Antilopini gen. and
331 sp. indet.), although Fiume Santo also supported some species (*M. lorenzi* and *M. cf. lorenzi*)
332 with strategies equalling those of extant mixed feeders. Based on molar wear data, there is no
333 evidence of grazing species in this interval. Since it occurred in different intervals, the signals
334 found in *M. haupti* can be a good indication that a different vegetation structure occurred in the
335 V1 and V2 habitats. Finally, dental wear patterns of post-*Oreopithecus* faunas indicate a shift to
336 new dietary heterogeneity (more similar to that of Baccinello V1), with the existence of
337 browsers (*P. cf. australis*), mixed feeders (*P. cf. loczyi* and *T. huerzeleri*), and species involved
338 in grazing (*H. malpassii*) as well. That is, the new species of Baccinello V3 were apparently
339 more engaged in grazing than those that co-evolved with *Oreopithecus*.

340 Overall, the widest range of dietary traits is observed in Baccinello V1 and V3, with species
341 clearly representing two dietary categories (browsing and mixed feeding) described by
342 Hofmann and Stewart (1972) and one adaptation close to grazing. This would indicate that
343 species partitioned their resources by occupying different niches within the local environment
344 and feeding on different foods (Schoener, 1974). In contrast, less diversity in feeding
345 adaptations is observed in Baccinello V2 and Fiume Santo, where there are herbivores
346 representing only browsing and mixed feeding, the former being the most common diet adopted
347 by the species. More specifically, the *Oreopithecus* communities (that is, Baccinello V1,
348 Baccinello V2 and Fiume Santo) consist of 66.6% of species with a browsing dietary signature
349 and some additional (33.3%) mixed feeders, some of which are particularly pronounced in grass
350 consumption. On the other hand, the post-*Oreopithecus* community (Baccinello V3) has 25%
351 species that correspond to browsers, whereas 75% correspond to mixed feeders or taxa which
352 are engaged in grazing. It is worth noting that the more homogeneous character of the diets in
353 V2 cannot be explained as a matter of taphonomical homogeneity (if compared with the other
354 levels). Indeed, our V2 sample is represented by the same number of localities as V1 (Podere la
355 Crocina, Montebamboli and Fiume Santo vs. Casteani, Ribolla and Serrazzano, respectively).

356 The key difference among V1 and V2 is not due to the number of localities in which they
357 belong, but instead to the taxonomical composition of the fauna, as there are very few species
358 that are found in common (Rook et al., 2011) (Table 1). This is due to the arrival of new
359 immigrants into the region and to the appearance of new species resulting from in situ
360 evolutionary transformation of locally endemic forms (i.e., *Maremmia haupti*/*Maremmia*
361 *lorenzi*) (Rook et al., 2011). By and large, what can be seen (Fig. 4C) is that the ungulate
362 composition is dominated by Bovidae in V1, by Bovidae+Giraffidae in V2, and by
363 Perissodactyla (Equidae) in V3. In this last assemblage, also evident is the relative reduction of
364 Bovidae and the appearance of Cervidae.

365 With regard to hypsodonty, we do not see any clear evolutionary pattern in this trait
366 according to the different time intervals examined here, since all the assemblages contain (at
367 least) mesodont and hypsodont species. This means that the hypsodont condition is already
368 evident in V1 and V2 assemblages, and that it is not an exclusive condition of *Hippotherium* in
369 V3, though this equid was probably better adapted to exploit the grass than other older
370 hypsodont bovids. It must be noted, however, that brachydont taxa occur for the first time in
371 Baccinello V3, but this probably does not correlate with any change in the environmental
372 conditions of the ecosystems, but with a different community structure because the arrival of
373 cervids of mainland origin (*P. cf. australis* and *P. cf. loczyi*) that are characterised by a natural
374 lower degree of hypsodonty than the remaining species (Janis, 1988). That is, the arrival of
375 more brachydont herbivores does not necessarily reflect a change in the vegetation (i.e., more
376 soft/ligneous foods) and in the nature of the landscape (i.e., more forested). This is because
377 tooth crown height is not always correlated with a higher degree of dietary abrasion (and
378 thereby with the mastication of high fiber and silica-rich grasses and/or exogenous soil and grit)
379 in the fossils, as most of the browsers (e.g., *E. vialli*, ?Antilopini gen. and sp. indet., *T.*
380 *gracillimus*, etc.) are mesodont (HI of 1.5-3) and even hypsodont species (HI > 3). This
381 theoretically suggests that a factor other than dietary abrasion (grass and exogenous particles
382 content in diet) is associated with increased hypsodonty and supports recent alternative
383 hypotheses (DeMiguel et al., 2015) for the origin and function of this trait.

384

385 4.2. *New thoughts on the climatic and environmental evolution of the Tusco-Sardinian*
386 *paleobioprovince*

387 All these results allow us to update and significantly improve our knowledge of the
388 dynamics of the basin, which is of utmost relevance to help reconstruct the circumstances that
389 ultimately led to the extinction of *Oreopithecus* and its associated fauna.

390 A first important phenomenon to highlight is the diverse range of feeding traits in ruminants
391 from Baccinello V1 (including specialists and generalists) whose dental wear signatures reflect
392 a variable forest landscape for this interval. Data are thus consistent with the presence of
393 arboreal plant taxa that commonly grow on slightly moist substrates (trees, shrubs, bushes, etc.)
394 and also open areas, potentially offering both browse and abrasive (such as grass) resources.

395 It is worth noting that such an ecological diversity apparently declined after this stage, as
396 denoted by a decrease of the wear scores and a restriction to a rather narrower range of food
397 items consumed among herbivores from Baccinello V2 (and Fiume Santo). Both the
398 homogeneity in the relative abrasive nature of the diets and the much higher proportion of
399 typical browsing signatures indicate that more closed (and less arid) habitats evolved after
400 Baccinello V1. Also, the absence of grazing ruminants, the shortage of mixed feeder species,
401 and the fact that these latter were not as committed to grazing as previous taxa, presumably
402 point to a lower development of grasses and forbs (Hofmann and Stewart, 1972; Merceron et
403 al., 2010). In addition, soft, ligneous material, such as woody twigs and leaves from trees and
404 shrubs, soft shoots, etc., seems to have been more commonly incorporated in diets, probably
405 during the entire year, since mesowear reflects dietary habits and abrasiveness during an
406 extended portion (several months to years) of the animal's life (Fortelius and Solounias, 2000;
407 Kaiser, 2003). This general tendency towards soft-leafy browsing diets and narrower ecological
408 divergence is consistent with two possible explanations. On the one hand, this could be merely
409 an artefact of the higher taxonomic diversity of Fiume Santo, since the number of species being
410 recorded in this locality is much higher than that of Baccinello V1 and V2. Alternatively, it is
411 possible that a shift towards increasing humidity could have forced species to specialise in less

412 abrasive plant species in patchy, forested environments. In any case, if such a climatic event did
413 occur, it would not have been accentuated enough and would not have caused a drastic change
414 in habitat structure and composition, as there were still some generalist species (*Maremmia*
415 spp.) in Fiume Santo that ate grass and abrasives to a certain degree.

416 Finally, our results provide compelling evidence for a new shift towards some ecological and
417 dietary variability in the post-*Oreopithecus* localities, which may be due to a somewhat more
418 varied mosaic of habitats in Baccinello V3. Bernor et al. (2011) suggested a mesic forest (i.e.,
419 habitat with a moderate or well-balanced supply of moisture) for Baccinello V3, with either a
420 considerably less seasonal rainfall and temperature regime or, alternatively, more permanent,
421 buffered water sources such as rivers and lakes. The fact that *H. malpassii* consistently ate a
422 substantial amount of grass of relatively low abrasive character (and hard items as well)
423 suggests some loss of canopy cover and increase of open areas. Even so, our data suggest the
424 existence of a forested environment, as browse was an important resource of the diet of most of
425 the ruminants of Baccinello V3. A forest habitat for this time interval is indeed consistent with
426 precipitation values for Baccinello V3 (van Dam, 2006). Our interpretation that a vegetation
427 change did take place and that it was not drastic enough to substantially alter the vegetation
428 composition of the landscapes is also in agreement with previous results (Matson et al., 2012)
429 based on the stable carbon and oxygen isotope record from organic matter in paleosols from the
430 Baccinello Basin. It is reasonable to assume therefore that *Hippotherium* would prefer more
431 open patches of this ecosystem, which is in agreement with the high $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values obtained for
432 this equid in the post-extinction localities (Nelson and Rook, 2016). Tooth enamel carbon and
433 oxygen analyses for *Hippotherium* (Bernor et al., 2011) revealed that this equid was an
434 intermediate-feeder with extensive grass components and abrasives in its diet, which is also in
435 accordance with our data from dental mesowear. The comparison with other East-Central
436 European species of *Hippotherium* (*H. sumegense* from the Pannonian Basin, Bernor et al.,
437 1999; *H. kammerschmittae* and *H. primigenium* from Dorn-Dürkheim, Kaiser et al., 2003; *H.*
438 *primigenium* from Höwenegg, Kaiser, 2003; and *H. intrans* from Rudabánya, Bernor et al.,

439 2003) further suggested that the species from Baccinello V3 was not as committed to browsing
440 as these populations, although it was considered similar to *H. primigenium* from Eppelsheim
441 (Germany) (Kaiser, 2003) and, especially, to *H. microdon* from Baltavar (Hungary) (Kaiser and
442 Bernor, 2007). Our data for Baccinello V3, however, do not accord well with some
443 interpretations based on isotopic data (Nelson and Rook, 2016). If a significant component of
444 the diet of the genera (e.g., *Hippotherium*, *Procapreolus*, *Tuscomeryx*) were grasses, carbon
445 isotopes would typically yield values indicative of significant grazing. Instead, Nelson and
446 Rook (2016) report a shift to lower $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values in the post-extinction localities, and they
447 conclude that an increase in forests with greater canopy cover took place in Baccinello V3.
448 However, the isotopic values recorded by one specimen of *Hippotherium* ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values of -
449 22.9‰) considered in their study is consistent with the presence of grasslands in V3, which is
450 indeed in agreement with our findings for this level. Other probable reasons for the apparent
451 discrepancy between tooth mesowear and the inorganic carbonate study by Nelson and Rook
452 (2016) may be the fact that dental mesowear and stable isotopic signals provide dietary
453 information at different temporal scales, with tooth mesowear usually corresponding to a longer
454 scale than isotopes (Davis and Pineda Munoz, 2016), as the temporal scale of this latter strongly
455 depends on the sampling protocol for analysis (Hoppe et al., 2004).

456

457 4.3. Understanding climate's influence on the extinction of *Oreopithecus*

458 Our study lends support to the hypothesis that the environmental evolution of the Baccinello
459 Basin during the late Miocene (8.3 to 6.4 Ma) was more heterogeneous than proposed (Matson
460 et al., 2012), as we detect here some ecological (and dietary) changes in the mammal
461 communities. From 7.1 Ma onwards, there was a change that favored the establishment of more
462 closed areas in Baccinello (where soft-ligneous foods were the most plentiful, although not the
463 only resource) and the occurrence of a ruminant association engaged in browsing. After that (ca.
464 6.7 Ma), the new fauna of Baccinello V3 reflects the existence of a slight but perceptible shift,
465 with a phase of development of open-country, arid-adapted herbaceous plants (and a certain loss
466 of canopy cover)—although still dominated by forested conditions. Although C4 grasses are not

467 detected in the Mediterranean region, this shift from V2 to V3 levels can be easily related to the
468 global vegetation change from C₃ grasses and forbs to C₄ herbaceous plants (mostly grasses)
469 recorded about 7 Ma ago (Cerling et al., 1997). The central question is, therefore, whether the
470 extinction of the last great ape in Europe was a direct result of such a shift in vegetation and
471 climate at ca. 6.7 Ma. To explore the possibility that a change of this nature may have perturbed
472 the specific conditions under which this primate lived, it is necessary to first understand the
473 ecological and food requirements of *Oreopithecus*.

474 On the one hand, plant macrofossils (Gaudin and Strozzi, 1858) and palynological
475 (Harrison and Harrison, 1989; Benvenuti et al., 1994) evidence of the succession of the
476 Baccinello-Cinigiano Basin indicate that *Oreopithecus* likely inhabited lowland mixed
477 mesophytic forests with a rich understory of small trees and shrubs and an herbaceous ground
478 cover, interrupted by freshwater pools and shallow lakes at some localities, as confirmed by the
479 abundance of algae and aquatic angiosperms. A remarkable fact is the scarcity of grasses and
480 open patches in V1 and V2 (Harrison and Harrison, 1989), even though these become more
481 abundant in V3 (Benvenuti et al., 1994). The paleobotanical evidence fits well with our
482 environmental reconstruction based on dental wear patterns of the ruminants, but contrasts with
483 our proposed landscape in one respect, as we find evidence of open patches and occurrence of
484 grasses in V1.

485 On the other hand, several studies have explored the molar microwear patterns of
486 *Oreopithecus* in an attempt to reconstruct its dietary proclivities. A diet strongly committed to
487 folivory (i.e., leaf-based) requiring high bite forces has been traditionally assumed (Ungar and
488 Kay, 1995; Carnieri and Mallegni, 2003). However, more recent studies have suggested the
489 alternative hypothesis of a coarser and more abrasive diet (Galbany et al., 2005; Williams,
490 2013), and even a predominantly terrestrial diet incompatible with specialised leaf-eating
491 (Nelson and Rook, 2016), which agree with the microwear research of DeMiguel et al. (2014)
492 that has led to the interpretation of *Oreopithecus* as an eclectic (frugivore/mixed feeder)
493 hominoid, rather than a strict folivore. More specifically, it seems to have relied heavily on soft
494 fruits but also foraged periodically on a wide range of foods, possibly due to the trophic

495 restrictions of its insular habitat in Tuscany and Sardinia. Although the marked development of
496 molar shearing crests in this taxon was interpreted as a folivorous (i.e., leaf-feeding)
497 specialisation (Ungar and Kay, 1995), its pronounced dental relief and the development of a
498 molar centroconid and other accessory cusps, crests and cingula (Zanolli et al., 2017) and
499 moderately thick enamel (Zanolli et al., 2016), more closely resemble those of omnivorous
500 suoids rather than folivores (Moyà-Solà and Köhler, 1997; Alba et al., 2001), which bear on its
501 recently proposed eclectic diet (Galbany et al., 2005; Williams, 2013; DeMiguel et al., 2014).
502 When more evidence is taken into account, *Oreopithecus* shows a number of striking
503 postcranial features (such as a short broad pelvis and femur with significant bicondylar angles
504 or tucked-in knees) and a hand with human-like precision grip capability which have been
505 interpreted by some authors as adaptations to bipedal locomotion (Straus, 1963; Moyà-Solà and
506 Köhler, 1997; Moyà-Solà et al., 2005; Rook et al., 1999b; but see Harrison, 1986, 1991;
507 Jungers, 1987). This could have favored more efficient terrestrial foraging in *Oreopithecus* and
508 the interaction with a greater range of food items than traditionally thought, probably including
509 arboreal soft-fruits, and leaves, grasses, herbs close to ground, hard objects, etc.(DeMiguel et
510 al., 2014). This is noteworthy for our central question, because the potential to adapt to climatic
511 instability and changing environments in eclectic (both recent and extinct) species is higher than
512 in specialised ones (DeMiguel et al., 2010). This is because climatic changes may thus compel
513 opportunistic taxa to forage alternative foods through flexible dietary strategies in order to
514 survive under new conditions, while a high emphasis (or dependence) on a single type of
515 resource may ultimately predispose a highly specialised taxon to extinction when the lack of
516 preferred foods occurs. If *Oreopithecus* was a highly folivorous taxon, it is likely that any
517 change (subtle or not) in its preferred habitat and food resources ultimately caused its extinction.
518 However, we can presume that *Oreopithecus* was able to adapt to a subtle change in climate and
519 persist in time more easily than previously expected due to a versatile diet including leaves and
520 fruits (Galbany et al., 2005; Williams, 2013; DeMiguel et al., 2014), and even terrestrial foods
521 (Nelson and Rook, 2016). Furthermore, its potential capacity to forage on some hard foods also
522 (probably C₃ grasses), as reported in DeMiguel et al. (2014), could have been an advantage in

523 light of the substantial proportion of grass of relatively low abrasive character and harder items
524 that appeared in the V3 biozone. According to all this, the fact that *O. bambolii* went extinct
525 could be informative that things other than a change in plant composition occurred in the
526 Baccinello Basin.

527 We have provide new data here, that can be used to reject the hypothesis of environmental
528 change as a main factor in the extinction of *Oreopithecus* and the associated endemic fauna.
529 These data can be analyzed together with previous results derived from other works to re-
530 evaluate and further refine the most parsimonious explanation for the decline and extinction of
531 *Oreopithecus*. Assemblage V3 records a time of tectonic collision of the Tusco-Sardinina
532 province, the establishment of extensive land connections with neighboring paleoprovinces and
533 the creation of inland seas that facilitated biotic interchanges with continental Europe (Rook,
534 2016). This faunal change marks the moment when the Corso-Sardinian massif was definitively
535 isolated from southern Tuscany by the opening of the Tyrrhenian Sea, and southern Tuscany
536 became fully connected with the newly formed Apennine chain.

537 We demonstrate that an environmental change is not likely to be the cause of the extinction
538 of *Oreopithecus* and the Maremma fauna. Convincingly demonstrating what did cause the
539 extinction is outside the scope of this study, since our analyses cannot directly support any
540 alternative hypothesis and other techniques of data analysis must be used for this purpose.
541 However, and as other authors (Bernor et al., 2001; Agustí, 2007; Abbazzi et al., 2008; Rook,
542 2009; Rook et al., 2011) have argued in a more extensive way, the arrival of continental
543 newcomers to the Tusco-Sardinian province seems to be the most parsimonious alternative
544 explanation. Thus, and although all the available evidence indicates that not one of the V2
545 mammalian elements are associated with the faunal complex of V3 (Rook et al., 2011; Rook,
546 2016), which makes testing difficult, it is probable that large predators and potential competitors
547 found in Baccinello V3 localities encountered the insular forms on a short (non-geological)
548 timescale. There are, therefore, two non-mutually exclusive hypotheses that can explain the
549 extinction. On the one hand, the arrival of the colobine monkey *Mesopithecus* at ca.7 Ma (Rook,
550 2009; Alba et al., 2015) may have led to strong competition and have had a serious impact on

551 *Oreopithecus*. On the other, *Oreopithecus* may also have been subject to potential predation by
552 the large saber-toothed *Machairodus* (Rook et al., 1999a), as felids are among the most
553 prominent predators of modern primates across the world (Hart, 2007; Meloro and Elton, 2012).
554 It is therefore highly probable that, if the opportunity arose, this terrestrial large predator would
555 take and consume *Oreopithecus* and other associated large herbivores. Although this theory
556 obviously needs further testing (for example through the examination of tooth marks on or
557 breakage patterns of bones of *Oreopithecus*), it emphasizes the role of faunal interactions when
558 an insular ecosystem establishes a connection with the continent, which may be more important
559 than ecological and climatic changes per se.

560

561 4.4. Comparison with the extinction of other European hominoids

562 Unlike the extinction of most other Miocene hominoids from Western and Central Europe
563 (ca. 9.5 Ma), that of *Oreopithecus* did not coincide with any major drastic climatic shift, but
564 rather to a local loss in canopy cover with development of open patches ca. 6.7 Ma. The
565 extinction of Miocene great apes in Spain and Central Europe has been associated with the
566 Vallesian Crisis (Agustí and Moyà-Solà, 1990; Casanovas-Vilar et al., 2011; Agustí et al., 2013;
567 DeMiguel et al., 2014), probably as a consequence of a climate shift towards increased
568 seasonality and aridity, which ultimately led to an increase in environmental uniformity and the
569 restriction and fragmentation of their preferred habitats (Alba, 2012; Marmi et al., 2012;
570 DeMiguel et al., 2014). In Eastern Europe, a few hominoids survived longer (8.0-7.5 Ma),
571 probably due to specialised (dietary and locomotor) adaptations to open and arid habitats
572 (Merceron et al., 2010). Similarly to that of *Oreopithecus*, their extinction did not coincide with
573 a strong directional change in climate but rather to strong variations in seasonality (Merceron et
574 al., 2013). The paleoenvironmental changes leading to the extinction of Eastern European
575 hominoids were apparently opposite to those experienced in Western and Central Europe, since
576 in Greece bushy vegetation expanded over areas previously occupied by grasslands, whereas in
577 Spain and Central Europe they were, instead, accompanied by the substitution of (sub)tropical
578 elements by more deciduous forests.

579

580 **5. Conclusions**

581 The present study on dental wear patterns and hypsodonty of herbivorous communities from
582 Tusco-Sardinian late Miocene localities (Baccinello-Cinigiano Basin, Fiume Santo) provides
583 compelling evidence of the existence of two different shifts in vegetation and climate during the
584 late Miocene in the area; one between 8.1 and 7.1 Ma (transition from V1 to V2 assemblages)
585 and other at ca. 6.7 Ma, this latter matching the extinction of *Oreopithecus* and the observed
586 faunal renewal. While a mosaic of habitats was represented in Baccinello V1 (as denoted by the
587 presence of strict browsers, mixed feeders and species engaged in grazing), a development of
588 more closed forests and less open areas seems to have occurred in Baccinello V2, as well as in
589 the correlated locality of Fiume Santo (as denoted by a much higher proportion of browser
590 species, a shortage of mixed feeders and an absence of grazers). After that, there was a partial
591 loss of canopy cover and a slight development of more open and drier areas in Baccinello V3
592 (as shown by the tendency towards grazing assumed for *Hippotherium* and several species with
593 intermediate diets), including the development of grasses of relatively low abrasive character.
594 Even so, our data suggest the existence of forests with more open canopy cover in the post-
595 extinction interval (as browse was an important component in the diet of most of the ruminants).
596 Despite these differences in feeding ecology between the ungulates associated with
597 *Oreopithecus* and those of a mainland origin, the change in climate that took place at some point
598 in the extinction interval was apparently not drastic enough to lead to intensive forest loss and
599 habitat fragmentation, or alter in a substantial way the vegetation of the local environment of
600 *Oreopithecus*, although it probably influenced its behaviour and lifestyle in some way.

601 Our dental wear and hypsodonty results confirm the existence of shifts in habitat and
602 climate, thereby providing evidence of certain similarity with the contemporaneous loss of
603 forests associated with other Miocene hominoid extinctions. However, we find that such a loss
604 of canopy cover (and/or development of more open parts) in the Baccinello Basin was not so
605 drastic as to ultimately lead to the extinction of *Oreopithecus*, even when considering its
606 coarser diet (i.e., trophic flexibility), recently proposed on the basis of dietary research.

607 It can be concluded that, although a coincident shift in habitat and climate took place, this
608 change was not likely the cause of the extinction event. Instead, direct competition and
609 predation by large terrestrial taxa (e.g., the colobine *Mesopithecus* or the felid *Machairodus*) as
610 a result of the influx of a new mainland community of vertebrates into the region (which
611 occurred as a consequence of tectonic collision of the Tusco-Sardinian province with mainland
612 Italy) emerges as a viable explanation for the disappearance of *Oreopithecus bambolii* and the
613 specialised, endemic Maremma fauna.

614

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873

874 **Figure legends**

875 **Figure 1. Schematic maps.** Outline of Italy (left) showing the regions of Tuscany and Sardinia
876 Island. The inset (right) shows an enlargement of the northern Tyrrhenian area, with the
877 geographical position of the fossiliferous localities mentioned in the text. A cluster of sites such
878 as Podere la Crocina, Ribaldella, Podere Firenze, Podere La Locca, Podere Le Pigne, Fosso del
879 Pian Calcinaio and Galassi are all located in between the hamlets of Baccinello and Cinigiano
880 (modified from Rook, 2016)

881

882 **Figure 2. Bivariate plot of hypsodonty index against mesowear score.** Hypsodonty data and
883 mesowear scores for extant species obtained, respectively, from Janis (1988) and Fortelius and
884 Solounias (2000). Colored symbols denote the interval to which each species belongs, black
885 symbols representing extant taxa. For those fossil species for which HI was not calculated (due
886 to the lack of suitable lower third molars), we assigned the value of the same species from
887 another locality.

888

889

890 **Figure 3. Cluster analysis based on dental wear features.** Hierarchical cluster based on the
891 percentage of high occlusal relief, round cusps and blunt cusps. Data on extant species from
892 Fortelius and Solounias (2000). Symbols and colors as in Figure 2.

893

894 **Figure 4. Results of the CVA based on three extant dietary categories and mesowear**
895 **variables.** Results based on dietary conservative (A) and radical (B) classifications. Data on
896 extant species from Fortelius and Solounias (2000). The ellipses showing the variability of
897 extant dietary categories (browsers, mixed feeders and grazers) are depicted in black. Larger
898 symbols denote group centroids. Symbols and colors as in Figure 2. The radical assignment of
899 the species informs about a possible foraging specialisation (i.e., dietary tendency) of the more
900 generalist species.

901

902 Tables

903 **Table 1. Summary of dental mesowear and hypsodonty results.**

Assemblage (age) / sites	Species	n	pH	pL	pS	pR	pB	MS	n	HI
<u>Baccinello V1</u> (8.3–8.1 Ma)										
Casteani, Ribolla, Serrazzano	<i>Umbrotherium azzarolii</i>	1	100	0	100	0	0	0		
	<i>Maremmia haupti</i>	10	33.3	66.6	43.8	56.2	0	1.718		
	<i>Turritragus casteanensis</i>	4	57.1	42.9	57.1	42.9	0	1.285	1	4.80
<u>Baccinello V2</u> (7.1–6.7 Ma)										
Podere la Crocina, Montebamboli	<i>Maremmia haupti</i>	2	50	50	100	0	0	1.25		

Fiume Santo (7.1–6.7 Ma)	<i>Tyrrhenotragus gracillimus</i>	7	90.9	9.1	70	30	0	0.4	2	3.40
	<i>Umbrotherium azzarolii</i>	36	98	2	94.9	5.1	0	0.068	5	1.72
	<i>Maremmia lorenzi</i>	2	100	0	0	100	0	1	2	4.98
	<i>Maremmia cf. lorenzi</i>	61	62.9	37.1	46.8	50	3.2	1.186	13	5.11
	<i>Tyrrhenotragus gracillimus</i>	16	100	0	84.7	15.3	0	0.153	5	3.39
	<i>Etruria viallii</i>	9	100	0	100	0	0	0	1	2.10*
	<i>Turritragus casteanensis</i>	2	100	0	100	0	0	0		
	?Neotragini gen. and sp. indet.	13	95.45	5.54	89.47	10.52	0	0.237	1	3.95
Baccinello V3 (6.7–6.4 Ma)										
Ribaldella, Podere Firenze,	<i>Hippotherium malpassii</i>	9	23.5	76.5	52.9	47.1	0	1.764	1	2.91*
Podere La Locca, Cinigiano,	<i>Paracervulus cf. australis</i>	4	100	0	57.1	42.9	0	0.428	1	1.3
Podere Le Pigne, Galassi and	<i>Tuscomeryx huerzeleri</i>	3	100	0	25	75	0	0.75	1	0.58*
Fosso del Pian Calcinaio	<i>Procapreolus cf. loczyi</i>	5	100	0	28.6	71.4	0	0.714	1	1.45

904 Abbreviations: Number of specimens measured (N); percentage of specimens with high (pH)
905 and low (pL) occlusal relief; percentage of specimens with sharp (pS), rounded (pR) and blunt
906 (pB) cusps; mesowear score (MS); Hypsodonty Index (HI); tentative assessment of HI (*).
907
908 **Table 2. Results of the CVA based on mesowear features.** The first value corresponds to the
909 analysis using a conservative classification; the second value refers to the analysis using a
910 radical dietary classification.

CV	Eigenvalue	Variance (%)	Cumulative variance (%)	Canonical correlation
CV1	2.148/2.265	91.0/98.3	91.0/98.3	0.826/0.833
CV2	0.213/0.039	9.0/1.7	100.0/100.0	0.419/0.195
Standardized coefficients of the CV				
CV	High relief	Rounded cusps		Blunt cusps
CV1	-0.746/-0.472	0.916/1.044		0.335/0.657
CV2	0.553/0.023	0.666/0.574		0.060/-0.550
Non-standardized coefficients of CV				
CV	High relief	Rounded cusps	Blunt cusps	Constant
CV1	-0.035/-0.020	0.043/0.049	0.029/0.056	0.288/-1.457
CV2	0.026/0.001	0.032/0.027	0.005/-0.047	-3.967/-1.229
Scores for group centroids				

CV	Browsers	Mixed feeders	Grazers
CV1	-2.025/-1.672	-0.228/-0.569	2.174/1.781
CV2	-0.624/-0.205	0.393/0.260	-0.382/-0.073

911 Abbreviations: canonical variate (CV).

912

913 **Table 3. Results of the discriminant analysis (and predicted group) according to the**
914 **mesowear features.**

Taxon	Assemblage	Conservative predicted group	<i>p</i>	D ²	Radical predicted group	<i>p</i>	D ²
<i>Umbrotherium azzarolii</i>	V1	B	0.373	1.971	B	0.138	3.960
<i>Maremmia haupti</i>	V1	G	0.533	1.257	MF	0.497	1.400
<i>Turritragus casteanensis</i>	V1	MF	0.291	2.471	MF	0.956	0.089
<i>Maremmia haupti</i>	V2	B	0.105	4.512	B	0.461	1.551
<i>Tyrrhenotragus gracillimus</i>	V2	B	0.908	0.194	B	0.983	0.035
<i>Umbrotherium azzarolii</i>	FS	B	0.548	1.203	B	0.248	2.788
<i>Maremmia lorenzi</i>	FS	MF	0.149	3.808	G	0.258	2.712
<i>Maremmia cf. lorenzi</i>	FS	MF	0.443	1.627	MF	0.867	0.285
<i>Tyrrhenotragus gracillimus</i>	FS	B	0.845	0.337	B	0.523	1.296
<i>Etruria viallii</i>	FS	B	0.373	1.971	B	0.138	3.960
<i>Turritragus casteanensis</i>	FS	B	0.373	1.971	B	0.138	3.960
?Neotragini gen. and sp. indet.	FS	B	0.736	0.613	B	0.413	1.771
<i>Hippotherium malpassii</i>	V3	G	0.265	2.654	MF	0.634	0.910
<i>Paracervulus cf. australis</i>	V3	B	0.663	0.823	B	0.929	0.147
<i>Tuscomeryx huerzeleri</i>	V3	MF	0.802	0.440	MF	0.616	0.968
<i>Procapreolus cf. loczyi</i>	V3	MF	0.881	0.254	MF	0.733	0.623

915 Abbreviations: Baccinello V1 (V1); Baccinello V2 (V2); Fiume Santo (FS); Baccinello V3

916 (V3); Squared Mahalanobis distance (D²); browsers (B); mixed feeders (MF); grazers (G).

Euclidean Distances

1 **Table 1. Summary of dental mesowear and hypsodonty results.**

Assemblage (age) / sites	Species	n	pH	pL	pS	pR	pB	MS	n	HI
<u>Baccinello V1</u> (8.3–8.1 Ma)										
Casteani, Ribolla, Serrazzano	<i>Umbrotherium azzarolii</i>	1	100	0	100	0	0	0		
	<i>Maremmia haupti</i>	10	33.3	66.6	43.8	56.2	0	1.718		
	<i>Turritragus casteanensis</i>	4	57.1	42.9	57.1	42.9	0	1.285	1	4.80
<u>Baccinello V2</u> (7.1–6.7 Ma)										
Podere la Crocina, Montebamboli	<i>Maremmia haupti</i>	2	50	50	100	0	0	1.25		
	<i>Tyrrenotragus gracillimus</i>	7	90.9	9.1	70	30	0	0.4	2	3.40
<u>Fiume Santo</u> (7.1–6.7 Ma)										
	<i>Umbrotherium azzarolii</i>	36	98	2	94.9	5.1	0	0.068	5	1.72
	<i>Maremmia lorentzi</i>	2	100	0	0	100	0	1	2	4.98
	<i>Maremmia cf. lorentzi</i>	61	62.9	37.1	46.8	50	3.2	1.186	13	5.11
	<i>Tyrrenotragus gracillimus</i>	16	100	0	84.7	15.3	0	0.153	5	3.39
	<i>Etruria viallii</i>	9	100	0	100	0	0	0	1	2.10*
	<i>Turritragus casteanensis</i>	2	100	0	100	0	0	0		
	?Neotragini gen. and sp. indet.	13	95.45	5.54	89.47	10.52	0	0.237	1	3.95
<u>Baccinello V3</u> (6.7–6.4 Ma)										
Ribaldella, Podere Firenze,	<i>Hippotherium malpassii</i>	9	23.5	76.5	52.9	47.1	0	1.764	1	2.91*
Podere La Locca, Cinigiano,	<i>Paracervulus cf. australis</i>	4	100	0	57.1	42.9	0	0.428	1	1.3
Podere Le Pigne, Galassi and	<i>Tuscomeryx huerzeleri</i>	3	100	0	25	75	0	0.75	1	0.58*
Fosso del Pian Calcinaio	<i>Procapreolus cf. loczyi</i>	5	100	0	28.6	71.4	0	0.714	1	1.45

2 Abbreviations: Number of specimens measured (*n*); percentage of specimens with high (pH)
3 and low (pL) occlusal relief; percentage of specimens with sharp (pS), rounded (pR) and blunt
4 (pB) cusps; mesowear score (MS); Hypsodonty Index (HI); tentative assessment of HI (*).

5

Table 2. Results of the CVA based on mesowear features. The first value corresponds to the analysis using a conservative classification; the second value refers to the analysis using a radical dietary classification.

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CV2	0.213/0.039	9.0/1.7	100.0/100.0	0.419/0.195
Standardized coefficients of the CV				
CV	High relief	Rounded cusps	Blunt cusps	
CV1	-0.746/-0.472	0.916/1.044	0.335/0.657	
CV2	0.553/0.023	0.666/0.574	0.060/-0.550	
Non-standardized coefficients of CV				
CV	High relief	Rounded cusps	Blunt cusps	Constant
CV1	-0.035/-0.020	0.043/0.049	0.029/0.056	0.288/-1.457
CV2	0.026/0.001	0.032/0.027	0.005/-0.047	-3.967/-1.229
Scores for group centroids				
CV	Browsers	Mixed feeders	Grazers	
CV1	-2.025/-1.672	-0.228/-0.569	2.174/1.781	
CV2	-0.624/-0.205	0.393/0.260	-0.382/-0.073	

Abbreviations: canonical variate (CV).

Table 3. Results of the discriminant analysis (and predicted group) according to the mesowear features.

Taxon	Assemblage	Conservative predicted group	<i>p</i>	D²	Radical predicted group	<i>p</i>	D²
<i>Umbrotherium azzarolii</i>	V1	B	0.373	1.971	B	0.138	3.960
<i>Maremmia haupti</i>	V1	G	0.533	1.257	MF	0.497	1.400
<i>Turritragus casteanensis</i>	V1	MF	0.291	2.471	MF	0.956	0.089
<i>Maremmia haupti</i>	V2	B	0.105	4.512	B	0.461	1.551
<i>Tyrrhenotragus gracillimus</i>	V2	B	0.908	0.194	B	0.983	0.035
<i>Umbrotherium azzarolii</i>	FS	B	0.548	1.203	B	0.248	2.788
<i>Maremmia lorenzi</i>	FS	MF	0.149	3.808	G	0.258	2.712
<i>Maremmia cf. lorenzi</i>	FS	MF	0.443	1.627	MF	0.867	0.285
<i>Tyrrhenotragus gracillimus</i>	FS	B	0.845	0.337	B	0.523	1.296
<i>Etruria viallii</i>	FS	B	0.373	1.971	B	0.138	3.960
<i>Turritragus casteanensis</i>	FS	B	0.373	1.971	B	0.138	3.960
?Neotragini gen. and sp. indet.	FS	B	0.736	0.613	B	0.413	1.771
<i>Hippotherium malpassii</i>	V3	G	0.265	2.654	MF	0.634	0.910
<i>Paracervulus cf. australis</i>	V3	B	0.663	0.823	B	0.929	0.147
<i>Tuscomeryx huerzeleri</i>	V3	MF	0.802	0.440	MF	0.616	0.968
<i>Procapreolus cf. loczyi</i>	V3	MF	0.881	0.254	MF	0.733	0.623

Abbreviations: Baccinello V1 (V1); Baccinello V2 (V2); Fiume Santo (FS); Baccinello V3

(V3); Squared Mahalanobis distance (D²); browsers (B); mixed feeders (MF); grazers (G).